

DEVELOPMENT OF LOW-CARB ICE CREAM

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 21

Issue 3

Pages: 305-316

Document ID: 2024PEMJ1963

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12540284

Manuscript Accepted: 06-20-2024

Development of Low-Carb Ice Cream

Angelika S. Salisi*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

Most of the Filipino loves to eat the Ice Cream for dessert but the existing ice cream have high sugar content. The research study focused on the development of low carb ice cream and identified the level of acceptability of the product among the local consumers or the respondents. Descriptive developmental research design was used in the study. The respondents were grouped into four age bracket categories 10-12 years old student in the elementary level, 13-16 years old student in the high school level, 17-21 years old student in the college level, and 22-32 years old experts / professionals to identify their levels of acceptability on the product. The ingredients use in develop low carb ice cream are available in home and supermarket are All-Purpose Cream, Cocoa Powder (unsweetened), Low Carb Sugar and Low-Fat Milk. The findings of the study about the respondent's level of acceptability about the product were highly acceptable by all age levels and gender in terms of Taste, Appearance, Packaging, and Costing. More importantly, it was found out that the level of acceptability of the product in terms of texture was an acceptable ages 17-21 years old low among the respondents in the college level and the rest were all high in all ages and in both genders. Moreover, the acceptability level of Low-Carb Ice Cream when respondents are group according to Age and Sex found not significantly different. It is therefore recommended that improvement of the of ice cream texture be given extra consideration.

Keywords: *development of low-carb ice cream, descriptive developmental research*

Introduction

Ice cream is one of the most favorite comfort food of Filipinos of all ages. Its sweetness, the ecstatic flavor and overwhelming feeling that it gives, that you want to have more. Due to the accessibility and affordability of this product there is negative impact among consumers especially on their health, too much consumption of this product might lead to some metabolic disorder or syndrome such as diabetes, abdominal obesity, and hypertension.

Metabolic syndrome also known as insulin resistance syndrome is a group of conditions that together raise your risk of coronary heart disease, diabetes, stroke, and other serious health problems. Metabolic syndrome has several causes, and each affects the other. You can control some of these causes, such as your diet and physical activity levels. Other causes, such as your age and your genes, cannot be controlled.

The metabolic syndrome (MetS) represents a clustering of risk factors for cardiovascular diseases that includes abdominal obesity, hypertension, dyslipidemia, and insulin resistance (Martin-Iguacel et al., 2016). It is usually diagnosed when at least 3 of the following conditions are present: hypertension, impaired fasting glucose (or impaired glucose tolerance or insulin resistance), central adiposity, systemic inflammation, decreased high-density lipoproteins, and elevated triglycerides. (Sangster, JM, et al.,2018).

Several definitions for Metabolic Syndrome have been developed, which can make comparison between separate studies difficult. Of the definitions of Metabolic Syndrome, the most widely used are the National Cholesterol Education Program Adult Treatment Panel III (NCEP ATP III) and the International Diabetes Federation (IDF). However, a consensus between the American Heart Association/National Heart, Lung and Blood Institute (AHA/NHLBI), and IDF has recently elaborated the AHA/NHLBI definition of Metabolic Syndrome.

One of the main causes of metabolic syndrome is an individual's weight. Your body might produce more of the molecules known as free fatty acids if you have fat cells, particularly in the abdomen. Your body's ability to regulate blood sugar levels can be impacted by other chemicals and hormones that are elevated by free fatty acids. Insulin, a hormone that regulates the amount of blood sugar absorbed by your muscles and organs, may not be absorbed by your body as well as it should. We refer to this as insulin resistance. Your "good" HDL cholesterol is lowered, and your "bad" LDL cholesterol is raised by free fatty acids and insulin resistance. Not only does insulin resistance increase blood pressure, but it can also boost lipid levels.

Additionally, immune system cells within your adipose tissue might produce substances that worsen inflammation throughout your body. A waxy material called plaque may accumulate inside your blood vessels because of this inflammation. Your blood arteries may get blocked by plaque that breaks off. Insulin resistance, hypertension, cardiac problems, and blood vessel disorders are all brought on by inflammation itself.

Your risk of metabolic syndrome is affected by some things you can control, such as your lifestyle habits, and some that you cannot control, such as your age or family history.

The primary line of treatment for metabolic syndrome is to adopt heart-healthy lifestyle choices. To help you find a diet and exercise

regimen that works for you, you might need to see a physical therapist and a dietitian. You might require medication or weight loss surgery if making healthy lifestyle changes does not work. Treatment for any medical issues that contribute to or could exacerbate your metabolic syndrome may also be necessary.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the Benefits of low carbs ice cream in usual ice cream. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 age; and
 - 1.2 sex?
2. What is the nutrient content and nutritional value of the sample Ice Cream?
3. What is the level of acceptability of the low carbs ice cream in terms of:
 - 3.1 taste;
 - 3.2 texture;
 - 3.3 appearance;
 - 3.4 packaging;
 - 3.5 costing; and
 - 3.6 shelf-life?
4. Is there any significant difference in the acceptability level of the low-carb ice cream according to Age and Sex of the respondents?
5. What improvement can be done to enhance the quality of the low-carb ice cream?

Methodology

This section present the research methodology, respondents of the study and the corresponding sampling techniques research instrument, procedure, and statistical treatment data.

Research Design

This study was descriptive developmental research since the final output is a developed low-carb ice cream. A developmental method was used in the study. Developmental research as opposed to simple instructional development, will define as “the systematic study of designing, developing and evaluating instructional programs, processes and products that must meet the criteria of internal consistency and effectiveness” (Google.com.ph) The research uses the IPO model (Input, Process and Output) to process of developing ice cream from raw materials / ingredients to final output/product.

Participants

The research study involved respondents from Barangay Balele, Tanauan City, Batangas consisting of 10 (Elementary Level), 10 (High School Level), 10 (College Level), 10 (30 and above Adults) and 2 (Experts) of Ice Cream maker.

Instruments

The study delved on two – part Survey questions.

Part 1. Is about the profile of the respondents in terms of age and sex. Part 2. Acceptability Level of the Low Carbs Ice Cream in terms of Taste, Texture, Appearance, Packaging, and Costing. To ensure the reliability and validity of the instrument it was subjected for validation by the 4 Master’s Teachers in Boot National High School. Furthermore, the final copy of the instrument was presented to the panel of expert for approval in using the stated instrument for the conduct of the study.

Data Procedure

The conceptualization and completion of the present study underwent several phases;

1. Development of Low Carb Ice Cream.

The first thing that the researcher do is to search the ingredients that have low carbs, then the researcher tries to make low carb ice cream using the ingredients that she searches, in consideration of the following; Taste, Texture, Appearance, Packaging and Costing. After that first trial, the researcher solicited the expertise of the Nutritionist to examined the Nutritional Value and Nutritional Content of Low Carbs Ice Cream. Likewise, the researcher interview via video calls the ice cream vendor regarding the quality of ice cream in terms of texture as seen in the first trial result indicating low quality of ice cream texture. To improve the texture of ice cream the researcher applies the strategy that she gets from the ice cream vendor, with emphasis on the following; 1. Proper mixing of mixture using hand mixer and time allotted for each mixing process. 2. Observance of proper storing in the refrigerator. 3. Remixing of the Low Carb Ice Cream with in 1 hour using spatula and then rest for 30 minutes in refrigerator and this is done for 3 times, to attain the desired

texture.

To ensure the equal portion of ice cream the researcher used digital weighing scale and plastic cup container. It took 7th trials to get the best result for developing of Low Carbs Ice Cream.

2. Seeking of Approval for the conduct of the Study.

Soon after the Development of Low Carbs Ice Cream, the researcher makes a Letter of Request for the Approval of conduct of the study with the corresponding Research Instrument, which was validated by the 4 Master's Teacher in Boot National High School.

3. Conduct of the study.

When the questionnaire is already validated the researcher distributed the questionnaire to the following respondents; 10 (Elementary), 10 (High School), 10 (College), 10 (Adult) and 2 (Experts) and administer the Taste-Test to all respondents. During the administration of the study the researcher make sure that the instructions in answering the questionnaire was clear and the respondents are properly guided all throughout the conduct of the study.

4. Gathering the Data

After the respondents answer the questionnaire, the researcher compiles the data by encoding their answer and submit the Data matrix to Statistic Center after seeking approval from the Statistician and the Adviser. The researcher waited for 7 to 10 days for the result of the Data.

5. Statistical Analysis.

After receiving the result, the researcher immediately analyst the result and start developing the chapter 4 after the evaluation.

Statistical Treatment of Data

To solve the problem of the study the following statistical tools were employed: To describe the profile of the respondent's frequency and percentages were used, while mean and standard deviation was utilized to determine the respondent's level of acceptability on the Taste, Texture, Appearance, Packaging, Costing of the low carb ice cream.

Furthermore, to compare the means of two or more independent groups the Kruskal-Wallis Test, also called the one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), was utilized to see if there is statistical support for the idea that the linked population means are significantly different.

When the dependent variable is either ordinal or continuous but not normally distributed, the Mann-Whitney U test was utilized to compare the differences across independent groups. In contrast to the independent-samples t-test, the Mann-Whitney U test lets you infer different conclusions about your data based on the distributional assumptions you choose. These findings can be as basic as declaring whether the two populations differ or as complex as figuring out whether the group medians differ. The shape of the distributions of your data, which we go into more detail about later, determines these disparate results.

Results and Discussion

The statistical analysis, interpretation, and discussion of the results are presented in this chapter. Finding out the respondents' profiles and the state of low-carb ice cream development are the main objectives. The main ideas outlined in the Problem Statement and the Study's Hypothesis guide the arrangement and display of the data that was gathered. The age and sex background information of the student responders is examined and studied.

The interpretation of the statistical analysis consists of analyzing and discussing the consequences of the data analysis results. The low-carb ice cream and the research objectives are explained, along with the results. The analysis of the study's advantages, disadvantages, and implications highlights the importance of the research and its implications for the creation of low-carb ice cream.

The results discussion included a comprehensive and insightful analysis of the data, as well as explanations, rationales, and plausible causes for any correlations or trends found. The findings were contextualized within the broader study by making analogies with other studies or theoretical frameworks.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents according to Age*

<i>Age Profile</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
10-12	10	23.8
13-16	10	23.8
17-21	10	23.8
22-32	12	28.6
Total	42	100.0

The distribution of the forty-two (42) respondents based on their age is shown in Table 1. Of them, ten (10) or 23.8% of the 10–12-year-olds, thirteen (16) of the 13–16-year-olds, seventeen (21) of the 17–21-year-olds, and twenty-two (32) of the 32–32-year-olds had

the greatest percentage of students taking part in the study.

Table 2. *Distribution of Respondents according to Sex Profile*

Age Profile	Frequency	Percentage
Male	24	57.1
Female	18	42.9
Total	42	100.0

Out of the forty-two (42) respondents, Table 2 displays the distribution of respondents based on their sex profile. Of the students that took part in the study, males made up twenty-four (24) or 57.1%, while females made up eighteen (18) or 42.9%. The results imply that a diverse sample of respondents provided the researcher with a range of responses. It implies that the research produced unbiased and perceptive results by presenting a variety of opinions from the diverse respondents' points of view.

Table 3. *Nutritional Value of Low Carb Ice Cream*

Ingredient	Quantity	Energy (kal)	Carbohydrate (g)	Protein (g)	Fat (g)	Sugar (g)	Fiber (g)	Calcium (g)	Iron (g)	Sodium (g)	Titanium (g)	Riboflavin (g)	Vitamin C
All Purpose Cream	500ml	1,328.00	20.00	12.00	132.00	20.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	0
Cocoa Powder Unsweetened	30g	127.50	7.50	7.50	3.75	-	15.00	-	-	7.50	-	-	0
Low Fat Milk Sweetener Substitute	180ml	68.40	9.36	6.48	0.58	-	-	216.00	-	90.00	-	-	0
		1,598.13	54.56	26.55	136.33	35.99	15.00	216.00	-	97.50	-	-	-

This table lists the nutrients in each cup of low-carb ice cream and shows how much of each nutrient is contributed to the daily value (% DV) in a normal diet. People can better comprehend the food item's nutritional makeup and how it fits into their daily nutrient requirements by using this table.

Below is an explanation of each column's meaning:

1. **Nutrient Content per Cup:** The amount of each nutrient in one cup of the food item is listed in this column. It indicates, for instance, that 159.81 calories, 5.46 grams of carbs, 2.66 grams of protein, and so on are included in one cup.
2. **% Daily Value:** The percentage of each nutrient's daily recommended intake that one cup of the food item provides is shown in this column. It is predicated on a daily diet of 2,000 calories, which is the norm for nutrition labeling in many nations. It demonstrates, for example, that one cup supplies 7.76% of the daily value for calories, 7.91% for carbs, 6.17% for protein, and so on.

Table 4. *Nutrient Content of Low Carb Ice Cream*

Nutrient Content per cup		% Daily Value
Energy (kcal)	159.81	7.76
Carbohydrate (g)	5.46	7.91
Protein (g)	2.66	6.17
Fat (g)	13.63	45.44
Sugar (g)	3.60	7.09
Fiber (g)	1.50	9.38
Calcium (mg)	21.60	2.16
Iron (mg)	-	0
Sodium (mg)	9.75	42.39
Thiamin (mg)	-	0
Riboflavin (mg)	-	0
Vitamin C	-	0

This table lists the components used in a recipe, their corresponding amounts, and the amount of nutrients in each serving. This table provides a thorough overview of the recipe's nutritional makeup, assisting in comprehension of its dietary composition and the formulation of wise consumption decisions. It can be seen in the table that the developed low carb ice cream consists of only 5.46 grams nutritional content per cup. It implies that it contains a very low carbohydrate content as compared to the existing commercialized ice cream which consists of 15-17 grams.

Moreover, the developed low carb ice cream also composed of low sugar level of 3.60 grams per cup. Meanwhile, the commercialized

ice cream consists of 12g-15g per 73g serving size. It can be demonstrated that the developed low carb ice cream is more preferred to eat to avoid high sugar content per serving size.

Table 5. Acceptability on Low Carb Ice Cream in terms of Taste when group based on Age

Indicators	10-12			13-16				17-21			22-32		
	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation	SD	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation	
Is pleasant	5.00	0.00	Highly Acceptable	5.00	0.00	Highly Acceptable	5.00	0.00	Highly Acceptable	4.75	0.45	Highly Acceptable	
Bears a sweet flavor	4.00	0.42	Highly Acceptable	4.50	0.53	Highly Acceptable	4.10	0.99	Acceptable	4.33	0.65	Acceptable	
Is wonderful to retain the natural flavor	5.00	0.00	Highly Acceptable	4.90	0.32	Highly Acceptable	4.70	0.67	Highly Acceptable	4.67	0.49	Highly Acceptable	
Has the blended taste of two main ingredients	4.90	0.32	Highly Acceptable	4.90	0.32	Highly Acceptable	4.70	0.67	Highly Acceptable	4.50	0.67	Highly Acceptable	
Is comparable to other ice cream in the market	5.00	0.00	Highly Acceptable	4.90	0.32	Highly Acceptable	4.50	0.53	Highly Acceptable	4.50	0.67	Highly Acceptable	
Overall	4.94	0.13	Highly Acceptable	4.84	0.21	Highly Acceptable	4.60	0.45	Highly Acceptable	4.55	0.47	Highly Acceptable	

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Highly Acceptable; 3.50-4.49 Acceptable; 2.50-3.49 Moderate; 1.50-2.49 Rarely; 1.00-1.49 Not Acceptable

This table displays the findings from an analysis of four separate groups or conditions' worth of ice cream's various qualities. Groups 10–12 had the greatest mean score of 4.94 and Group 22–32 the lowest mean score of 4.55, indicating that the ice cream was well regarded across all aspects based on the overall mean scores for each group. All mean scores, however, show that the ice cream is highly acceptable. Except for those aged 17 to 21 and 22 to 32, who ranked the taste of the ice cream as Acceptable. Children whose age ranges up to 15 love to eat ice cream in the Philippines according to Just Food (2020). Hence, it is expected that age groups of 17 to 21 and 22 to 32 have only an acceptable perspective about the taste of the developed low carb ice cream.

Table 6. Acceptability of Low Carb Ice Cream in terms of Texture when group based of Age

Indicators	10-12			13-16				17-21			22-32		
	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation	SD	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation	
Smooth or creamy	4.50	0.32	Highly Acceptable	4.80	0.42	Highly Acceptable	4.80	0.42	Highly Acceptable	4.50	0.87	Highly Acceptable	
Stretchy or gummy	4.80	0.63	Highly Acceptable	4.50	0.71	Highly Acceptable	3.40	1.35	Moderate	3.75	1.54	Acceptable	
Grainy or rough	4.70	0.67	Highly Acceptable	4.70	0.95	Highly Acceptable	3.20	1.75	Moderate	3.83	1.34	Highly Acceptable	
Chunky or hard	4.90	0.32	Highly Acceptable	4.80	0.63	Highly Acceptable	3.00	1.63	Moderate	3.83	1.40	Acceptable	
Is soft	4.90	0.32	Highly Acceptable	4.90	0.32	Highly Acceptable	3.74	1.12	Acceptable	4.25	0.87	Acceptable	
Overall	4.84	0.39	Highly Acceptable	4.74	0.51	Highly Acceptable	3.74	1.12	Acceptable	4.03	1.09	Acceptable	

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Highly Acceptable; 3.50-4.49 Acceptable; 2.50-3.49 Moderate; 1.50-2.49 Rarely; 1.00-1.49 Not Acceptable

In this table, four groups or conditions' worth of ice cream textures are evaluated. Groups 10–12 had the greatest mean score of 4.84 since this age group has the highest consumption of ice cream and Group 17–21 the lowest mean score of 3.74, indicating that the ice cream was acceptable for its texture based on the overall mean scores. It can be derived from the table that the two age groups specifically 17-21 and 22-32 are at the acceptable range only in terms of its texture. It can be attributed that these age groups are at the appropriate stage to arrive at the correct judgment as to whether the developed low carb ice cream has a good texture or not. Most students below age 17 are fond of eating sweets regardless of the quality of the product. According to Begum et al. (2020), younger child loves to eat ice cream and children prefer the taste of ice cream regardless of its other attributes.

Table 7. Acceptability of Low Carb Ice Cream in terms of Appearance when group based of Age

Indicators	10-12			13-16				17-21			22-32		
	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation	SD	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation	
Looks appealing	4.90	0.32	Highly Acceptable	4.90	0.32	Highly Acceptable	4.90	0.32	Highly Acceptable	4.83	0.39	Highly Acceptable	
Looks delicious or mouthwatering	4.90	0.32	Highly Acceptable	4.50	0.71	Highly Acceptable	4.60	0.70	Highly Acceptable	4.75	0.45	Highly Acceptable	
Looks clean and palatable	4.90	0.32	Highly Acceptable	5.00	0.00	Highly Acceptable	4.50	0.63	Highly Acceptable	5.00	0.00	Highly Acceptable	
Is uniform in color	5.00	0.00	Highly Acceptable	5.00	0.00	Highly Acceptable	4.90	0.32	Highly Acceptable	4.83	0.39	Highly Acceptable	
Is well-mixed and portioned	5.00	0.00	Highly Acceptable	4.70	0.67	Highly Acceptable	5.00	0.00	Highly Acceptable	4.83	0.39	Highly Acceptable	
Overall	4.94	0.13	Highly Acceptable	4.82	0.27	Highly Acceptable	4.84	0.31	Highly Acceptable	4.85	0.24	Highly Acceptable	

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Highly Acceptable; 3.50-4.49 Acceptable; 2.50-3.49 Moderate; 1.50-2.49 Rarely; 1.00-1.49 Not Acceptable

In this table, four groups or conditions' assessments of the ice cream's presentation and visual appeal are shown. Group 10–12 had the greatest mean score of 4.94 and Group 13–16 had the lowest mean score of 4.82. The total mean scores for each group indicate that the ice cream's visual presentation was highly rated across all attributes. It only implies that the developed low carb ice cream is visually appealing to all age groups. However, according to Syed et al. (2018), there is need of further research in field of ice cream manufacturing to establish further improvements in overall appearance along with physical characteristics to meet the changing demands of consumers and decorate the ice cream with chocolate pieces, roasted nuts, and many other food items.

Table 8. Acceptability of Low Carb Ice Cream n terms of Packaging when group based of Age

Indicators	10-12			13-16				17-21			22-32		
	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation	SD	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation	
The packaging drew shoppers' attention	4.90	0.32	Highly Acceptable	4.70	0.48	Highly Acceptable	4.80	0.42	Highly Acceptable	4.87	0.49	Highly Acceptable	
The product is shield from the elements by its packing	5.00	0.00	Highly Acceptable	4.90	0.32	Highly Acceptable	4.90	0.32	Highly Acceptable	4.75	0.62	Highly Acceptable	
Customers may find all the information they need to know about the product on the box	5.00	0.00	Highly Acceptable	4.70	0.48	Highly Acceptable	4.50	0.71	Highly Acceptable	4.75	0.62	Highly Acceptable	
The package is done simply but artistically.	5.00	0.00	Highly Acceptable	4.80	0.42	Highly Acceptable	4.00	0.52	Highly Acceptable	4.75	0.62	Highly Acceptable	
The product is highlighted by the straightforward packaging	4.90	0.32	Highly Acceptable	4.90	0.32	Highly Acceptable	4.80	0.42	Highly Acceptable	4.83	0.39	Highly Acceptable	
Overall	4.98	0.13	Highly Acceptable	4.80	0.23	Highly Acceptable	4.72	0.38	Highly Acceptable	4.75	0.45	Highly Acceptable	

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Highly Acceptable; 3.50-4.49 Acceptable; 2.50-3.49 Moderate; 1.50-2.49 Rarely; 1.00-1.49 Not Acceptable

Four groups or conditions' worth of product packaging assessments are shown in this table. Groups 10–12 had the greatest mean score of 4.96 and Group 17–21 the lowest mean score of 4.72, indicating that the product's packaging was well regarded across all criteria based on the overall mean scores for each group. All mean scores, show that the packaging is highly acceptable. According to Barman et al. (2017), it may be due to the difference sanitary practices adopted in different ice cream plants and outlets during manufactures, packaging, storage, and distribution of the product and due to ingredient added after pasteurization of the mix (color, essence, fruit, nuts, sauce, etc.). In this regard, the developed low carb ice cream is well-packaged since the existing cup appropriate for the storage of the product was used.

Table 9. Acceptability on Low Carb Ice Cream in term of Costing when group based on Age

Price	10-12		13-16		17-21		22-32	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
Php 11-16	4	40.0	-	-	-	-	-	-
Php 17-22	-	-	-	-	2	20.0	-	-
Php 23-28	-	-	-	-	1	10.0	4	40.0
Php 29-34	-	-	10	100.0	7	70.0	6	60.0
Php 35-40	6	60.0	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total	10	100.0	10	100.0	10	100.00	10	100.0

This table shows the respondents' preferred price range distribution for each of the four groups or situations. The 13 to 16 group ages 10 of respondents choose 29 to 34 pesos with (100%) , 17-21 group ages 7 of respondents with (70%) choose also the 29 to 34 pesos and 22-32 grouped ages 6 of the respondents with (60%) prepare range in 29 to 34 pesos as costing price of develop low carbs ice cream. It implies that the perspectives of the respondents are suitable to acquire profits when the developed low-carb ice cream is introduced in the market. The total expense per cup is Php 10.00, thus, there is at least 200% profit if the ice cream is sold from Php 30-Php 34.

Table 10. Summary Table on the Acceptability of Low Carb Ice Cream when group according to Age

Indicators	10-12			13-16			17-21			22-32		
	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation	SD	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Taste	4.94	0.13	Highly Acceptable	4.84	0.21	Highly Acceptable	4.50	0.45	Highly Acceptable	4.55	0.47	Highly Acceptable
Texture	4.84	0.39	Highly Acceptable	4.74	0.51	Highly Acceptable	3.74	1.12	Acceptable	4.03	1.09	Acceptable
Appearance	4.94	0.13	Highly Acceptable	4.82	0.27	Highly Acceptable	4.84	0.31	Highly Acceptable	4.85	0.24	Highly Acceptable
Packaging	4.95	0.13	Highly Acceptable	4.80	0.23	Highly Acceptable	4.72	0.38	Highly Acceptable	4.75	0.45	Highly Acceptable
Overall	4.92	0.19	Highly Acceptable	4.80	0.31	Highly Acceptable	4.47	0.56	Acceptable	4.54	0.56	Highly Acceptable

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Highly Acceptable; 3.50-4.49 Acceptable; 2.50-3.49 Moderate; 1.50-2.49 Rarely; 1.00-1.49 Not Acceptable

In this table, four groups or conditions' worth of ice cream features are evaluated. The ice cream was highly acceptable in the first two groups (10–12 and 13–16) across all qualities, according to the total mean scores for each group. Though flavor and packaging were consistently scored well, there was a decline in satisfaction with texture and appearance in the later groups (17–21 and 22–32). Due to the ingredients of all-purpose cream, it produces rough texture. Dairy-free frozen desserts have experienced strong growth, with many traditional ice cream companies releasing plant-based alternatives (Mintel, 2019). Plant-based frozen desserts may be perceived as healthier, even if their nutritional content is otherwise like their dairy counterparts (Bullock et al., 2020). Flavor is the key driver of liking in frozen desserts. Similarly, Bullock et al. (2020) investigated consumer liking and health perceptions of vegan frozen desserts and low-calorie or super-premium ice cream products.

Table 11. Acceptability on Low Carb Ice Cream in terms of Taste when group based on Age

Indicators	Male			Female		
	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Is pleasant	4.88	0.34	Highly Acceptable	5.00	0.00	Highly Acceptable
Bears a sweet flavor	4.54	0.59	Highly Acceptable	4.28	0.83	Acceptable
Is wonderful to retain the natural flavor	4.79	0.41	Highly Acceptable	4.83	0.51	Highly Acceptable
Has the blended taste of two main ingredients	4.71	0.55	Highly Acceptable	4.78	0.55	Highly Acceptable
Is comparable to other ice cream in the market	4.71	0.55	Highly Acceptable	4.72	0.46	Highly Acceptable
Overall	4.73	0.38	Highly Acceptable	4.72	0.39	Highly Acceptable

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Highly Acceptable; 3.50-4.49 Acceptable; 2.50-3.49 Moderate; 1.50-2.49 Rarely; 1.00-1.49 Not Acceptable

This table shows the ratings on the flavor of ice cream, broken down by Sex Profile. Both male and female respondents usually gave positive reviews to qualities such pleasantness, natural flavor retention, blended taste, and similarity to other ice creams, with mean scores suggesting highly acceptable. The male mean is higher the female of 1 %. According to Stokols et al. (2006) and Kilcast (2003) dealt with the differences in sensory evaluation based on biogenic factors, specifically, the age and gender. In older age groups the loss of sensory abilities was proved, to which the manufacturers should adapt the flavorings and ours characteristic of food.

This table shows the ratings of the textures of ice cream, broken down by Sex Profile. Both genders appeared to find the ice cream textures to be Acceptable overall, based on the overall mean scores for each gender, with females scoring slightly higher overall (4.42) than males (4.25). Creaminess can be defined as the determinant effect of a miscible, thick, smooth, slippery, and soft liquid in the mouth (Kilcast & Clegg, 2002). The pattern in which creaminess is sensed depends on many structural factors such as rheology, oil droplets size, incorporated air percentage, ice crystals number and size, etc. (Trgo, 2003). These factors are inevitably connected both

to the ice cream components and the adopted processing practices.

Table 12. Acceptability on Low Carb Ice Cream in terms of Texture when group based on Sex Profile

Indicators	Male			Female		
	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Smooth or creamy	4.71	0.55	Highly Acceptable	4.78	0.43	Highly Acceptable
Stretchy or gummy	4.00	1.32	Highly Acceptable	4.22	1.17	Acceptable
Grainy or rough	3.96	1.40	Highly Acceptable	4.28	1.32	Acceptable
Chunky or hard	4.04	1.40	Acceptable	4.22	1.31	Acceptable
Is soft	4.54	0.72	Highly Acceptable	4.61	0.98	Highly Acceptable
Overall	4.25	0.96	Acceptable	4.42	0.95	Acceptable

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Highly Acceptable; 3.50-4.49 Acceptable; 2.50-3.49 Moderate; 1.50-2.49 Rarely; 1.00-1.49 Not Acceptable

Table 13. Acceptability on Low Carb Ice Cream in terms of Appearance when group based on Sex Profile

Indicators	Male			Female		
	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Looks appealing	4.83	0.38	Highly Acceptable	4.94	0.24	Highly Acceptable
Looks delicious or mouthwatering	4.71	0.55	Highly Acceptable	4.67	0.59	Acceptable
Looks clean and palatable	4.88	0.45	Highly Acceptable	5.00	0.00	Highly Acceptable
Is uniform in color	4.88	0.34	Highly Acceptable	5.00	0.00	Highly Acceptable
Is well-mixed and portioned	4.92	0.26	Highly Acceptable	4.83	0.51	Highly Acceptable
Overall	4.84	0.26	Highly Acceptable	4.89	0.22	Highly Acceptable

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Highly Acceptable; 3.50-4.49 Acceptable; 2.50-3.49 Moderate; 1.50-2.49 Rarely; 1.00-1.49 Not Acceptable

This table shows ratings for the ice cream's presentation and visual appeal, broken down by Sex Profile. The ice cream's visual attractiveness and presentation were highly praised by both genders, based on the overall mean scores for each gender. However, women gave the ice cream a slightly higher overall mean score (4.89) than men (4.84). Appearance is the characteristic of ice cream that first influences consumer perception. Evaluation of the other sensory properties (aroma, taste, texture) must wait. As a major contributor to appearance, color is important to overall sensory appeal. Given that, color is an attribute that can draw customers towards any product and this explains that the visual evaluation of color usually takes place first out of all the other categories. According to Huang (2023), it is found that individuals preferred foods with warm-color filters (red and orange) over cool color filters (green and blue). From the study's findings, it can be inferred that there is a general tendency of individuals to prefer eating food with warm-color themes compared to cold-color themes.

Table 14. Acceptability on Low Carb Ice Cream in terms of Packaging when group based on Sex Profile

Indicators	Male			Female		
	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
The packaging drew shoppers' attention	4.79	0.41	Highly Acceptable	4.72	0.46	Highly Acceptable
The product is shield from the elements by its packing	4.79	0.51	Highly Acceptable	5.00	0.00	Highly Acceptable
Customers may find all the information they need to know about the product on the box	4.71	0.62	Highly Acceptable	4.78	0.43	Highly Acceptable
The package is done simply but artistically.	4.75	0.53	Highly Acceptable	4.83	0.38	Highly Acceptable
The product is highlighted by the straightforward packaging	4.83	0.38	Highly Acceptable	4.89	0.32	Highly Acceptable
Overall	4.78	0.37	Highly Acceptable	4.84	0.29	Highly Acceptable

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Highly Acceptable; 3.50-4.49 Acceptable; 2.50-3.49 Moderate; 1.50-2.49 Rarely; 1.00-1.49 Not Acceptable

Product packaging evaluations are shown here, with data broken down by Sex Profile. The overall mean scores for each gender indicate that both Male and Female gave the product's packaging good marks; however, female gave it a slightly higher overall mean score (4.84) than men (4.78). According to Van Rompay et al. (2018), research has mainly focused on how visual appearances steer sensory impressions including smell and taste. Considering new (technological) developments in packaging design, this research investigates the impact of 3D-printed surfaces on taste evaluation of two ice cream variants. In addition, the interplay between surface textures and matching or non-matching shapes presented on a poster in the consumption environment (i.e., an ice-cream salon) was studied.

This table shows the respondents' preferences, broken down by gender, for various price ranges. Price ranges are divided into the following PHP (Philippine peso) intervals by the table: PHP 11–16, PHP 17–22, PHP 23–28, PHP 29–34, and PHP 35–40. Male and Female: Every row denotes a distinct price range, and every column denotes a distinct gender.

The respondents that prepared costing 11 to 16 pesos are 3 with (12.5%) in Male while in female is 1 only with (5.6%). Then in 17 to 22 pesos are 2 with (11.1%) in female. In 23 to 28 pesos are 4 with (16.7%) in Male while in Female is 1 only with (5.6%) and in 29 to 34 pesos are 17 with (70.8%) in Male while in Female are 14 with (77.8%).

Table 15. *Acceptability on Low Carb Ice Cream in terms of Costing when group based on Sex Profile*

Price	Male		Female	
	F	%	F	%
Php 11-16	3	12.5	1	5.6
Php 17-22	-	-	2	11.1
Php 23-28	4	16.7	1	5.6
Php 29-34	17	70.8	14	77.8
Php 35-40	-	-	-	-
Total	24	100.0	18	100.0

Generally, both male and female choose the 29 to 34 pesos range of costing in develop low carbs ice cream. It implies that the perspectives of the respondents are suitable to acquire profits when the developed low-carb ice cream is introduced in the market. The total expense per cup is Php 10.00, thus, there is at least 200% profit if the ice cream is sold from Php 30-Php 34.

Table 16. *Summary Table on the Acceptability of Low Carbs Ice Cream when group according to Sex Profile*

Indicators	Male		Female			
	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Taste	4.73	0.38	Highly Acceptable	4.72	0.39	Highly Acceptable
Texture	4.25	0.96	Highly Acceptable	4.42	0.95	Highly Acceptable
Appearance	4.84	0.26	Highly Acceptable	4.89	0.22	Highly Acceptable
Packaging	4.78	0.37	Highly Acceptable	4.84	0.29	Highly Acceptable
Overall	4.65	0.49	Highly Acceptable	4.72	0.46	Highly Acceptable

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Highly Acceptable; 3.50-4.49 Acceptable; 2.50-3.49 Moderate; 1.50-2.49 Rarely; 1.00-1.49 Not Acceptable

This table presents assessments of several ice cream qualities, broken down by Sex Profile. Both male and female assessed the ice cream Highly Acceptable for all categories, except for texture. with female giving it a little higher overall mean score (4.72) than men (4.65). According to Bugge (2015), aspiring for health and fitness has become increasingly important for Norwegians. This is expressed in many ways. For instance, there has been a significant increase in the proportion who states that they are very interested in having a healthy diet. Furthermore, three out of ten stated that they had tried diets to achieve weight reduction over the past twelve months. One consequence of this trend is a consumption field that requires a multitude of products and services. This includes everything from food and dietary products that help you realize the dream of a sound, slim, strong, smart, and sexy body, to books, blogs and TV shows that guide the individual towards making the right food choices.

Table 17. *Test of Difference in the Acceptability Level of Low Carb Ice Cream when group based on Age*

	Taste	Texture	Appearance	Packaging	Pricing
Chi-square	7.273	8.745	1.291	3.540	5.511
DF	3	3	3	3	3
Asymp Sig.	.064	.033	.731	.316	.138

Significant difference only exists in terms of texture-Kruskal-Wallis Test

Table 17 shows the significant difference on the acceptable label of low carb ice cream when respondents are grouped according to age. Generally, the p-values for each attribute of low carb ice cream, namely Taste (0.064), Appearance (0.731), Packaging (0.316), and Pricing (0.138) indicate no significant differences among the stated qualities of ice cream except the texture with p-values of 0.033 which is less than 0.05. This implies that in considering the aged group of the respondents, the acceptability level of the low carb ice cream differs between and among the aged group in terms of texture. In studying closely, the level of acceptability of ice cream among aged group, this significant difference appears dominantly in age grouped between 17-22 to 22-32 acceptability level ranging from moderately acceptable to acceptable level only. Children whose age ranges up to 15 love to eat ice cream in the Philippines according to Just Food (2020) regardless of other attributes. However, age groups of 17 to 21 and 22 to 32 consider other characteristics or features of the food they eat. Hence, they have only an acceptable perspective about the texture of the developed low carb ice cream since manual mixing was used which affects the texture and creaminess of the low carb ice cream. According to Kilcast and Clegg (2002), the creaminess can be defined as the determinant effect of a miscible, thick, smooth, slippery, and soft liquid in the mouth.

Table 18. *Test of Difference in the Acceptability Level of Low Carb Ice Cream when group based on Sex Profile*

	Taste	Texture	Appearance	Packaging	Pricing
Mann-Whitney U	215.500	187.000	194.500	195.500	202.500
DF	-014	-797	-653	-622	-445
Asymp Sig.	.989	.425	.514	.534	.657

The table revealed that the p-values for taste, texture, appearance, packaging, and pricing are all relatively higher than p-0.05 which denotes that there is no significant difference on the level of acceptability of ice cream between male and female respondents. Generally, based on these results, it seems that the male and female respondents are most likely have the same level of acceptability of ice cream in terms of taste, texture, appearance, packaging, and pricing. The male and female are same in their response in acceptability level

of low carb ice cream.

Popular culture often portrays gender differences in food cravings, such as the notion that men crave savory foods (e.g., burgers) whereas women crave sweet foods (e.g., chocolate), especially as they approach menses (Bratskeir K. 2015). While this is not always the case, some research has supported gender differences in not only the type of food craved, but also in clinically-important characteristics of craving such as frequency, severity, and regulation of food craving (Osman JL et al. 2006) and (Lafay L et al. 2001). Men and women tend to crave different kinds of foods. Several studies have shown that men report more craving for savory foods (e.g., meat, fish, eggs), whereas women report more craving for sweet foods (e.g., chocolate, pastries, ice cream; (Zellner DA et al. 1999) and (Weingarten HP, Elston D. et al. 1991). Further, men may crave different types of sweets than women do (e.g., sugar-sweetened beverages, but not chocolate; (Zellner Daet al. 1999).

Conclusion

Since there is no significant variation in acceptability of Low Carb Ice Cream based on the respondents' age and sex, the hypothesis in this regard is supported with statistical evidence except for texture where significant difference existed.

In the light of findings and conclusion drawn for the study, the following recommendations were given; (1) To improve the general of acceptability of Ice Cream it might be of great help to explore on various binder use in developing Ice Cream. (2) The development of low-carb ice cream was generally highly accepted by the respondents across all ages and gender it can be used in Business. (3) Improvement of ice cream in terms of texture was needed to attain the highest acceptability level among the future clients.

References

- Alessandro Genovese et. al. (2022). Functional ice cream health benefits and sensory implications. Retrieved from:<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0963996922009164>
- Ali Mohammed Saadi et. al. (2022). USE OF NATURAL SWEETENERS (MAPLE SYRUP) IN PRODUCTION OF LOW-FAT ICE CREAM. Retrieved from:<https://keypublishing.org/jhed/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/22.-Full-paper-Ali-Mohammed-Saadi.pdf>
- Barman, A. K., Roy, P. K., Ray, S., Kumar, R., Rani, B., & Singh, B. K. (2017). Evaluation of microbiological quality of Ice-cream available in Kolkata and its Suburbs. *The Pharma Innovation*, 6(8, Part F), 377. Retrieved from:<https://www.thepharmajournal.com/archives/2017/vol6issue8/PartF/6-7-87-123.pdf>
- Begum, A., Palash, M. S., Alam, M. A., & Begum, M. (2020). Ice cream consumption in a selected area of Bangladesh: effect of demographic, psychometric and product factors. Retrieved from:<https://www.cabidigitallibrary.org/doi/full/10.5555/20203206112>
- Bowden, J., Sears, B., & Cole, W. (2020). *Living Low Carb: Revised & Updated Edition: The Essential Guide to Choosing the Right Low-Carb Plan for You*. Union Square & Co.. Retrieved from:https://books.google.com.ph/books?hl=en&lr=&id=tF21EAAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PT14&dq=low+carbs+ice+cream&ots=OA3PUq048m&sig=HotSYg5k1Q9a7CQtZq7pU-zDZKM&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q=low%20carbs%20ice%20cream&f=false
- Bugge, A. B. (2015). Why are alternative diets such as "low carb high fat" and "Super healthy Family" so appealing to Norwegian Food consumer. Retrieved from:<https://oda.oslomet.no/oda-xmlui/bitstream/handle/10642/4911/46491-160005-3-PB.pdf?sequence=1>
- Bratskeir K. (2015). "This is why women crave chocolate, men want a burger." [cited 2015 Nov 5]. Retrieved from: http://www.huffingtonpost.com/2014/11/10/chocolate-craving-pms-men-vegetables_n_6102714.html
- Dangcalan (2022). Chapter 3 Research Design and Methodology Population Sampling Retrieved from:https://www.academia.edu/40679561/CHAPTER_3_RESEARCH_DESIGN_AND_METHODODOLOGY_Population_Sampling
- Deosarkar & Sarode et. Al. (2016). Title Ice Cream: Uses Method of Manufacture Retrieved from:<https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/pharmacology-toxicology-and-pharmaceutical-science/emulsifying-agent>
- Dr. Nicholas Norwitz (2022) Low-Carb Diet Reverses Metabolic Syndrome, Independent of Weight Loss. Retrieved from:https://ketodietapp.com/Blog/lchf/low-carb-diet-reverses-metabolic-syndrome-independent-of-weight-loss-study-insight?fbclid=IwAR2ldJGjku0ZVIdMthAixLYPsB5sKSKU1bWPx-807z2Mb9g_K37tt1AGhY4
- Goff & Hartel, et. al. (2013). Stabilizer Retrieved from: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/87559129.2011.563399>
- Goff & Hartel (2013). "Ice Cream Structure." Retrieved from:[https://www.researchgate.net/publication/302209726_Ice_Cream_Structure#:~:text=...%20Ice%20cream%20is%20a%20complex%20frozen%20foam%20comprising%20ice,Goff%20%26%20Hartel%2C%202013a\)%20](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/302209726_Ice_Cream_Structure#:~:text=...%20Ice%20cream%20is%20a%20complex%20frozen%20foam%20comprising%20ice,Goff%20%26%20Hartel%2C%202013a)%20)
- Harvard T.H. Chan (2023) The Nutrition Source. Low-Calorie Sweeteners. Retrieved from:https://www.hsph.harvard.edu/nutritionsource/healthy-drinks/artificial-sweeteners/?fbclid=IwAR1Nagjhp-jeZ-8e0HnnvpSZENGPVAI7_JfpeeKXrqMS4NZN7sgaMsLzAqI
- Homayouni et al. (2018). "Advanced Method in Ice Cream Analysis." Retrieved from:<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s12161-018-1292-0>
- Huang (2023). A Study on the Effect of Color on Human Food Perception- Jingyi Huang Retrieved

- from:https://www.researchgate.net/publication/369867642_A_Study_on_the_Effect_of_Color_on_Human_Food_Perception
James et. al. (2014). Freezing and Frozen Storage. Retrieved from:https://www.researchgate.net/publication/344425934_Freezing_and_Frozen_Storage
- Jackie L. Boucher, et. al. (2020). JCL roundtable: Low-carbohydrate diets Retrieved from:<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S1933287420302257>
- John L. Sievenpiper (2020). Low-carbohydrate diets and cardiometabolic health: the importance of carbohydrate quality over quantity. Retrieved from:https://academic.oup.com/nutritionreviews/article/78/Supplement_1/69/5877749?fbclid=IwAR2LHHxStQMs5BmXuf1zLhgBixNq5Da2l_dpS-JhDn0TUVJt_XZG-8tb-UM&login=false
- Joshua, C., Lokesh, S., & Balasubramanian Ganesh (2022). Treating Type 2 Diabetes with Therapeutic Carbohydrate Restriction. Retrieved from: https://www.intechopen.com/online-first/83789?fbclid=IwAR3oPMe6cjOzPBzw61U5qD3GiUg-aj3yUK0a_Bnl61ujdSbYtXtflUt9Ps
- Just The Facts – Ice Cream In The Philippines. Retrieved from:<https://www.just-food.com/features/just-the-facts-ice-cream-in-the-philippines/?cf-view>
- Kilcast & Clegg, 2002. Factors affecting texture of ice cream Retrieved from:https://www.researchgate.net/publication/287434251_Factors_affecting_texture_of_ice_cream
- Kristin M Hirahatake, Arne Astrup, James O Hill, Joanne L Slavin, David B Allison, Kevin C Maki (2020). Potential Cardiometabolic Health Benefits of Full-Fat Dairy: The Evidence Base Retrieved from:<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2161831322002836?fbclid=IwAR3ljLqBS6c2Bh-VnKOnHEI1R7zAyYazy2cwIrR6C71u8MugIcwr4sSnc6k>
- Lafay L, et al. (2001). "Gender differences in the relation between food cravings and mood in an adult community: Results from the Fleurbaix Laventie Ville Sante study". Retrieved from:<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/11429982/>
- Mintel Ice cream and frozen novelties—US—May 2019
- Osman JL et al. (2006), Chocolate cravings in American and Spanish individuals: Biological and cultural influences. Retrieved from:<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/16831486/>
- Osorio-Arias & Martínez-Monteaudo et al. (2021). Book: Innovative Food Processing Technologies volume 3. Retrieved from:<https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/agricultural-and-biological-sciences/homogenization>
- Peter J. Foley (2021) Effect of low carbohydrate diets on insulin resistance and the metabolic syndrome. Retrieved from:https://www.researchgate.net/publication/353489870_Effect_of_low_carbohydrate_diets_on_insulin_resistance_and_the_metabolic_syndrome
- P.J. Fellows et al. (2017). Book: Food Processing Technology (Fourth Edition) Retrieved from:<https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/agricultural-and-biological-sciences/pasteurization>
- Richard D. Feinman, Mary Makowske (2003). Metabolic syndrome and low-carbohydrate ketogenic diets in the medical school biochemistry curriculum Retrieved from:<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/18370662/>
- Stokols et al. (2006) or Kilcast (2003) Sensory evaluation: Age and gender profiling of lite, no-sugar-added vanilla ice creams Retrieved from:https://www.researchgate.net/publication/230061398_Sensory_evaluation_Age_and_gender_profiling_of_lite_no-sugaradded_vanilla_ice_creams?fbclid=IwZXh0bgNhZW0CMTAAR1IizE_2w9nBFiu4VgZIrT9MhJ5QAqmRPZhp_UEFbhh6hJjA0151J6J8qI_aem_AQOmamj12jw79V70FMK2DcTvw_cquenZfwc4NTO6h7xSt_x--nnhS566GFk37S6LPUMVb6WN2hQhICA84p97bL5
- Shane A Bilsborough , Timothy C Crowe (2003). Low-carbohydrate diets: what are the potential short- and long-term health implications? Retrieved from:<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/14672862/>
- Stephen D. Phinney (Author), Jeff S. Volek (Author) (2011). The Art and Science of Low Carbohydrate Living: An Expert Guide to Making the Life-Saving Benefits of Carbohydrate Restriction Sustainable and Enjoyable Retrieved from:<https://www.amazon.com/Art-Science-Low-Carbohydrate-Living/dp/0983490708>
- Syed, Q. A., Anwar, S., Shukat, R., & Zahoor, T. (2018). Effects of different ingredients on texture of ice cream. Journal of Nutritional Health & Food Engineering, 8(6), 422-435. Retrieved from:https://www.researchgate.net/publication/330029461_Effects_of_different_ingredients_on_texture_of_ice_crea
- Van Rompay, T. J., Kramer, L. M., & Saakes, D. (2018). The sweetest punch: Effects of 3D-printed surface textures and graphic design on ice-cream evaluation. Food quality and preference, 68, 198-204. Retrieved from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0950329318301757>
- Wan Sulaiman, W. N. H., Ibrahim, A. A., Halim, N. A., Sulaiman, N. A. S., & Mohd Nor, M. I. (2022). Development and Sensory Evaluation of Dates Ice Cream. Multidisciplinary Applied Research and Innovation, 3(4), 10–14. Retrieved from: <https://penerbit.uthm.edu.my/periodicals/index.php/mari/article/view/9691>

Weingarten HP, Elston D. et al. (1991). "Food cravings in a college population". Retrieved from:<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/1799279/>

Wendy Pogozelski, Nicholas Arpaia, Salvatore Priore (2005). The metabolic effects of low-carbohydrate diets and incorporation into a biochemistry course Retrieved from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/21638552/>

Zelman, et. al. (2017). Emulsifiers Retrieved from: <https://foodandnutrition.org/november-december-2017/food-additives-emulsifiers/>

Zellner DA, Garriga-Trillo A, Rohm E. et al. (1999),"Food liking and craving: A cross-cultural approach". Retrieved from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/10447980/>

Zoe Atlas (2022). 5 low-carb ice creams less likely to spike your blood sugar Retrieved from:https://www.levelshealth.com/blog/5-low-carb-ice-creams?fbclid=IwAR3aBopZyC7uFVizu1AvKBf63nF7mNVjgRsfSgTS0wUmaFE7POMQw2lZf_c

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Angelika S. Salisi

Laguna State Polytechnic University – Philippines